

Overcoming the Selectivity-Sensitivity Trade-Off in Electroactive Gas Sensing Using Hybrid Glass Composites

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Hybrid glasses derived from meltable metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have emerged as a new class of amorphous materials. Combining the porosity of MOFs with the processing ability of glasses, they are thought to enable a wholly new range of functional compounds. By way of example, it is demonstrated here how the intrinsic porosity of glasses obtained from zeolitic imidazolates (ZIFs) can be used to overcome the selectivity-sensitivity trade-off in electroactive gas sensing. For this, composites are fabricated in which metallophthalocyanines are embedded within a ZIF-62 MOF glass matrix. Such a material enables the detection of gas species (or their absence) utilizing the pronounced electrochemical sensitivity of phthalocyanines. Thereby, the solid glass does not only stabilize and protect the active component, but also – through its retained, highly tunable porosity – ensures sensor selectivity by molecular sieving and targeted size exclusion of larger molecules. In addition, the hydrophobicity of the ZIF pore interior protects the active component from degradation caused by ambient humidity. Investigations of the structural, optical and electronic properties of the composite indicate that compoundation is purely physical, that is, chemical interactions between the compound partners are avoided and the individual properties of the hybrid glass matrix and the electroactive metallophthalocyanine are retained. Atmosphere-controlled high-temperature electrical impedance measurements reveal significant shifts in resistance in CO₂ and Ar atmosphere as compared to airflow. These results provide a proof of concept for sensitive and selective gas sensors based on such composites.

1. Introduction

Gaseous pollutants – even in very low concentrations – can be invisible and odorless threats to human health^[1,2] and the environment^[3] in general. Therefore, fast and effective detection is required in both science and industry, and fabricating gas sensors with sufficient performance is essential. However, there is usually a trade-off between sensitivity and selectivity,^[4,5] which is not easy to overcome: a highly sensitive sensing material might suffer from low selectivity, making it difficult to differentiate multiple gas species and avoid sensor bias and malfunction. Aiming at both sides of the trade-off separately, we now suggest that the sensitivity of electroactive compounds (such as metallophthalocyanines) and the selectivity of porous hybrid glasses (derived from metal-organic frameworks, MOFs) can be combined in a composite material in order to provide gas sensors with significantly improved performance.

MOFs are formed through the highly ordered assembly of inorganic metal ions or clusters coordinated by organic linkers via reticular synthesis.^[6] They often exhibit exceptional inner surface area and

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Figure 1. Crystal structures of a) ZIF-62 and b) PcCo. Gray, carbon; green, nitrogen; blue, zinc; pink, cobalt. Crystallographic data are taken from Refs.[44,45] c) EDX elemental mapping of Zn (top) and Co (bottom); the corresponding SEM image is shown in Figure S2 (Supporting Information). d) Optical images of pure a_g -ZIF-62, PZGC-05, PZGC-1, and PZGC-5 taken in transmittance mode.

large pore volumes, and their pore space can be chemically tailored and functionalized to control diffusion or accommodate target molecules for gas separation and storage applications.^[7,8] MOF-derived melt-quenched glasses are an emerging type of hybrid materials, currently expanding toward new examples of glass-forming sub-classes,^[9,10] melting strategies^[11,12] and first applications.^[13] The zeolitic imidazolate framework ZIF-62 ($[\text{Zn}(\text{Im})_{2-x}(\text{bIm})_x]$, Im = imidazole, bIm = benzimidazole) (Figure 1a), in particular, has been demonstrated to exhibit exceptionally high glass-forming ability (GFA) owing to its high viscosity at the melting temperature (T_m).^[14] Similar to their crystalline counterparts, ZIF-based glasses also offer permanently accessible porosity, which can be precisely tuned to create molecular-

sieving cut-offs between different guest species.^[15] The glassy nature allows for liquid-state shaping^[16] and fabrication of bulk samples, not suffering from grain boundary diffusion, which results in a drastic increase in selectivity.^[17,18] Composites of MOF-glasses with crystalline MOFs^[19] and inorganic glasses^[20,21] showed great material compatibility. Specifically, a_g -ZIF-62 (a_g – amorphous glass) proved as a possible matrix for photoluminescent materials – not only in enabling scalable bulk samples but by stabilizing active phases and therefore enhancing the luminescence efficiency. In addition, ZIF materials are known to be hydrophobic,^[23,24] which would exclude the risk of humidity damaging the sensor or affecting its performance.^[25,26] We suggest here that the aforementioned features make MOF-glass a

perfect candidate for sensitive electroactive composites, where it can act as a molecular sieve.

The sensitivity challenge is addressed through the electroactive agent – cobalt phthalocyanine, $C_{32}H_{16}CoN_8$ (PcCo) (Figure 1b). Metallophthalocyanines (PcMs) are optically active^[27,28] complexes demonstrating gas-sensing ability.^[29–32] They have been used as photosensitizers in photodynamic therapy for the production of cytotoxic reactive oxygen species in the near-infrared spectral range (600–700 nm).^[33] PcMs consists of four pyrrole rings bound to a central metal ion, allowing fine-tuning of their optical, electronic, and sensing properties.^[32,34,35] For example, Pc-M derivatives containing open-shell or paramagnetic metal ions such as Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , and Pd^{2+} exhibit short triplet lifetimes in the nanosecond range, while those containing closed d-shell or diamagnetic metal ions like Zn^{2+} , Al^{3+} , and Ga^{3+} exhibit high triplet yields with longer lifetimes exceeding 200 μs .^[36–38] Our choice of a cobalt-based compound, PcCo, is because of its chemical and thermal stability at high temperatures, which was demonstrated previously by incorporating PcCo into porous glass composite membranes for oxygen separation.^[39] Moreover, structurally modified PcCos (e.g., by polymerization or addition of functional groups) can exhibit high catalytic activity for the electrochemical reduction of carbon dioxide (CO_2).^[40–42] Composites of metallophthalocyanines with zeolites – structural forerunners of ZIFs – are known since the end of the 20th century^[43] and have also been tested as oxidation catalysts.

In this study, we consider functional PcCo crystals embedding within a porous a_g ZIF-62 matrix, demonstrating the utility of such a composite in gas sensing. In particular, we focus on its pronounced sensitivity to oxygen. Detecting a lack of oxygen is, for instance, crucial in poorly ventilated indoor workspaces, when its content in breathable air decreases with an increase in CO_2 – not only a greenhouse gas but also an asphyxiant. The hydrophobic nature of the MOF glass prevents penetration of ambient water to poison the PcCo compound, and its tailorable porosity selectively excludes larger molecules (such as nitrogen) that are dominantly present in ambient air from interacting with the sensor.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Synthesis, Structural Analysis and Characterization of PcCo@ a_g ZIF-62 Composites

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) coupled with thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of phthalocyanine (Figure S1, Supporting Information) was initially conducted in order to determine thermal properties. The DSC and TGA curves for PcCo showed no thermal effects up to 500 °C, which is above the melting temperature ($T_m \approx 450$ °C) of ZIF-62. Next, pellets were prepared by blending PcCo and pure ZIF-62 (see Methods for ZIF-62 synthesis) in different weight ratios, namely 0.5:100, 1:100, 5:100 mg, 10:100 mg, 20:100 mg, 30:100 mg, and 50:100 mg for melt-quenching experiments. Sample nomenclature and weight ratios are summarized in Table 1.

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) measurements and element mapping were performed on the sample PZGC-10 (Figure 1c; Figure S2, Supporting Information). The elemental

Table 1. Sample denotation and codes for prepared blends and melt-quenched glass composites.

Powder Name	Weight Ratio	Blend Code	Glass Composite Name	Glass Composite Code
ZIF-62	–	–	a_g ZIF-62	–
PcCo	–	–	–	–
PcCo@ a_g ZIF-62	0.5:100	PZB-05	PcCo@ a_g ZIF-62	PZGC-05
–	1:100	PZB-1	–	PZGC-1
–	5:100	PZB-5	–	PZGC-5
–	10:100	PZB-10	–	PZGC-10
–	20:100	PZB-20	–	PZGC-20
–	30:100	PZB-30	–	PZGC-30
–	50:50	PZB-50	–	PZGC-50

analysis shows the distribution of PcCo crystals in the form of faceted inclusions in a homogenous glass matrix. The atomic Zn/Co content of different spots on the surface, varying from point to point (Table S1, Supporting Information), indicates the heterogeneity of the composite on a micrometer scale. However, macroscopically the distribution of zinc and cobalt sites is relatively homogeneous (Figure 1c). The surface morphology of composites was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Figure S5, Supporting Information). An increase in the number of surface defects was observed with an increase in the content of PcCo crystals.

The melt-quenched compounds PZGC-05, PZGC-1, and PZGC-5 appeared purple to the naked eye (Figure S3, Supporting Information). In Figure 1d, optical microscopy images in transmittance mode confirm that the transparency of the PcCo@ a_g ZIF-62 samples, as expected, decreases with the amount of PcCo in the glass compositions. Top and cross-sectional microscope images of a_g ZIF-62 and PcCo@ a_g ZIF-62 samples are shown in Figure S4 (Supporting Information). The melting processes of ZIF-62 (Movie S1, Supporting Information), of the PZB-05 blend (Movie S2, Supporting Information), and the remelting process of PZGC-05 composite glass (Movie S3, Supporting Information) were recorded using a microscope-coupled heating stage to monitor changes. The ZIF-62 and PZB-05 blend powders are shrinking during melting, similar to our detailed examination on MOF glasses published previously.^[15] During the remelting of PZGC-05, the macroscopic flow of the composite piece was observed, leading to a shape transformation through the viscous flow of the ZIF-62 melt, embedding the PcCo. Compositional changes of PcCo@ a_g ZIF-62 samples with an increase of PcCo content are tracked through XRD (Figure 2a). Starting from fully amorphous neat a_g ZIF-62, the crystalline phase is detected in all composites: two intense diffraction lines are attributed to the (100) and (102) planes of β -PcCo ($2\theta = 7.17^\circ$ and 9.34° , respectively).^[46] Their increasing intensities correlate to the β -PcCo content; they indicate that there was no deformation or phase transformation in the phthalocyanine crystals during the melting of ZIF-62. These observations confirm the formation of a hybrid composite PcCo@ a_g ZIF-62, appearing as a physical mixture not suffering from undesired interactions or transformations.

Figure 2. a) XRD patterns of PZGC composites, and a_g -ZIF-62 and PcCo for comparison. b) DSC (solid lines) and TGA (dashed lines) scans of ZIF-62 and PZB-5. c) Raman spectra of a_g -ZIF-62 and PZGC-30. Blue arrows indicate characteristic peaks of PcCo. d) FTIR spectra of crystalline and melt-quenched ZIF-62, PZB-10, and PcCo for comparison. Blue stars indicate characteristic peaks of PcCo.

The effect of PcCo crystals on the melting kinetics of ZIF-62 was further investigated by DSC-TGA (Figure 2b). The DSC-TGA curves of the synthesized pure ZIF-62 and PZB-5 blend demonstrated the same offset melting temperature of ≈ 450 °C (Figure 2b), indicating that the presence of thermally stable PcCo does not affect the T_m values of the a_g -ZIF-62 in the analyzed glass composites. A separate C_p scan revealed the T_g to be at ≈ 331 °C for the PZGC-05 sample (Figure S6, Supporting Information) which agrees with our previous observations for a_g -ZIF-62.^[15,47]

The hybrid composites were also examined by Raman spectroscopy: results for a_g -ZIF-62 and PZGC-30 are compared in Figure 2c. The emerging peaks at 1341 and 1307 cm^{-1} are related to isoindole stretching in PcCo.^[48] Several other characteristic peaks of PcCo are also detected.^[49] The somewhat reduced intensity of the peak of a_g -ZIF-62 at 1278 cm^{-1} is related to the decreased symmetric stretching of the C–N bond of the organic linker (Figure 2c).^[50] In addition, the FTIR spectra of ZIF-62 and PZB-10 before and after melt-quenching are recorded; the spectrum of PcCo is also shown for comparison (Figure 2d). IR bands in PZB-10 and PZGC, corresponding to PcCo are indicated with the blue stars, including C–H out of plane bending at 732 cm^{-1} , C–C stretching in isoindole at 1332 and 1425 cm^{-1} , as well as C=N stretching at 1522 cm^{-1} of PcCo.^[51–53] Thus, the general structure of both components is preserved upon melt-quenching of the blend: the pattern of a pure ZIF-62 glass is reproduced (for instance, the disappearance of the peak at 1750 cm^{-1}) and the characteristic PcCo bands are still present. UV–vis absorbance measurements of a_g -ZIF-62, PZGC-05, and PZGC-1 also reveal the embedded PcCo phase with the character-

istic peaks of the Q band of phthalocyanines (600–750 nm) (Figure S7, Supporting Information),^[32] with a maximum at ≈ 715 nm, corresponding to PcCo.^[54] As expected, the optical absorbance increases when higher amounts of PcCo are embedded within the glass.

2.2. Impedance Spectroscopy and CO₂-Sensing Ability of PcCo@ a_g -ZIF-62

The PcCo@ a_g -ZIF-62 composites were studied using impedance spectroscopy in ambient air and a controlled atmosphere. Delocalization of the phthalocyanine macrocycle enables the displacement of π -electrons across the microcrystalline regions, resulting in increased polarizability and higher dielectric constant. Aromatic compounds with a strongly linked structure can cause non-madmic polarization due to the existence of significant amounts of free charges and long domains.^[55] As the temperature increases, the amount of free mobile charge carriers also increases in phthalocyanines.

Similar to our previous observation on a_g -ZIF-62,^[21] it was not possible to perform accurate measurement of conductivity and activation energy due to the lack of charge carriers in PZGC-10 (Figure S8, Supporting Information) within the temperature range of 100 – 200 °C. The conductivities of PZGC-20, PZGC-30, and PZGC-50 were found to be enhanced at elevated temperatures, as confirmed through the Nyquist plots shown in Figure 3a (PZGC-20) and Figure S8 (Supporting Information) (PZGC-10, PZGC-30 and PZGC-50). Arrhenius plots of electric conductivity

Figure 3. a) Nyquist plot of the electrical impedance in PZGC-20 for the temperature range of 100–200 °C. b) Arrhenius plot of the conductivity for PZGC-20, PZGC-30, and PZGC-50. Straight lines are the linear fits of the experimental data. Nyquist plots for PZGC-50 at 200 °C c) in Ar and air flows and d) in CO₂ and air flows. The labels “1st” and “2nd” indicate two sequential measurements.

for PZGC-20, PZGC-30, and PZGC-50 (Figure 3b) indicate that the conduction within this temperature range depends on PcCo concentration in the composites. The calculated activation energies and electrical conductivities are summarized in Table 2. The similar conductivity profiles of PZGC-30 and PZGC-50 point to a percolation effect of PcCo crystals in composite glasses, where the percolation threshold should be somewhere between PZGC-20 and PZGC-30.^[56]

Table 2. Electrical conductivity (σ), pre-exponential term (σ_0), and activation energy (E_a) of the PZGC-20, PZGC-30, and PZGC-50 composites. The error values of the ionic conductivity are related to measurement uncertainty and geometric factors, while the error values of the pre-exponential terms and activation energies are related to data fitting.

Sample	Log $\sigma_{200\text{ °C}}$ [Log(Scm ⁻¹)]	Log σ_0 [Log(Scm ⁻¹)]	E_a [eV]
PZGC-20	-10.5 ± 0.3	-3.3 ± 0.1	0.43 ± 0.01
PZGC-30	-8.7 ± 0.3	0.02 ± 0.07	0.57 ± 0.01
PZGC-50	-8.4 ± 0.3	1.5 ± 0.08	0.68 ± 0.01

Impedance spectroscopy measurements in a controlled atmosphere showed significant direct current resistance changes in Ar and CO₂ flows compared to air flows at 200 °C in PZGC-50. Nyquist plots of sequential measurements in Ar→Air and CO₂→Air flows are shown in Figures 3c,d. The conductivity (σ) values in Ar and CO₂ flows, $\approx 1.3\text{--}1.5 \times 10^{-8}$ Scm⁻¹, reduced to $\approx 2.3\text{--}3.2 \times 10^{-9}$ Scm⁻¹ with the air injections, which is related to adsorbed oxygen from the air. Despite the low precision of the used gas pump, the close conductivity values of sequential measurements show the stability of the composite. These results appear as a proof of concept for possible PcCo@*a*_gZIF-62 composites utilization as gas sensors.

3. Conclusion

Embedding the PcCo crystal into an *a*_gZIF-62 matrix during melt-quenching yielded hybrid PcCo@ZIF-62 glass composites. Impedance spectroscopy showed the utility of such material for selective gas sensing. For example, a lack of O₂ in the ambient atmosphere decreases the impedance of PcCo. The process of gas uptake and electroactive sensing is reversible, indicating that

the sensor material is deactivated by the interaction of the functional component with the detected gas. With improved spatial homogeneity of the composite, the resulting performance could be further increased, benefitting from tunable molecular sieving through the a_g -ZIF-62 matrix. In the case of oxygen leak sensing, the quantitatively dominant nitrogen is excluded by their size, and further, water (frequently degrading the PcCo functional component) by hydrophobicity of the matrix. As a perspective, chemical modification of the phthalocyanine can be used to adapt its sensitivity toward other gas species, such as known from the examples of induced CO₂ reduction. Given the nature of utilized materials – a highly tunable, porous glass matrix and an electroactive functional component – their combination can result in a composite overcoming the trade-off between sensitivity and selectivity of common gas sensors.

4. Experimental Section

Chemicals: N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF, ≥99.9%), dichloromethane (DCM, 99%+ extra pure) were purchased from Acros Organics B.V.B.A. Zn(NO₃)₂ • 6H₂O (99% metal basis) was delivered from ABCR GmbH & Co KG, Germany. Imidazole (Im, ≥99.5%), Benzimidazole (blm, 99% HPLC), and Cobalt (II) phthalocyanine (dye content 97%, β-form) were purchased from Merck KGaA (Sigma Aldrich).

Synthesis of ZIF-62: The ZIF-62 synthesis was based on our previous work.^[15] For synthesis, all chemicals were dissolved in a beaker containing 96.0 mL of DMF. The first 7.6055 g of Im was stirred until completely dissolved, and then 2.5571 g of blm was added and stirred until completely dissolved. Subsequently, 3.9869 g of Zn(NO₃)₂ • 6H₂O was added and the solution was stirred for another 10 min. The solution was transferred to a Teflon-lined autoclave (125 mL), sealed, and kept at 130 °C for 48 h. The resulting particles were washed twice with DMF and twice with DCM using glass vacuum suction filters. The sample was dried in a vacuum oven at 150 °C and 25 mbar for 2 days.

Synthesis of a_g -ZIF-62 and PcCo@ a_g -ZIF-62 Composites: To fabricate the glass composites, 100 mg of the blend of PcCo and ZIF-62 (see Table 1) were ground in a mortar and then pressed with a force of 0.7 tons for 1 min, resulting in pellets with a diameter of 1 cm. The prepared pellets were then placed between two glass slides using metal paper clips and transferred to a tube furnace (Carbolite) that was flushed with nitrogen gas during the heating and cooling processes. The tube furnace was heated at a rate of 10 °C per minute until it reached a temperature of 450 °C, at which point it was held for 5 min. Subsequently, the pellets were allowed to cool to room temperature.

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD): The Rigaku MiniFlex diffractometer with a Cu K α X-ray source and a wavelength of 1.54059 Å was used to collect XRD data from ZIF-62, PcCo, PZGC-1, and PZGC-10 in Bragg-Brentano geometry in the 2θ range of 5° to 50° and step size of 0.02°. 40 kV and 15 mA of voltage and current were set for the X-ray tube, respectively. XRD measurements of a_g -ZIF-62, PZGC-05, PZGC-5, PZGC-20, PZGC-30 were carried out with a PANalytical Empyrean DY1098 powder X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α radiation (1.5406 Å) in the θ - 2θ arrangement in the range of 5°–40° with a step size of 0.02°.

Thermogravimetric Analysis Coupled with Differential Scanning Calorimetry (TGA-DSC): A Netzsch STA 449 F1 instrument was used to perform the TGA and DSC analysis. 10–15 mg of each sample were gently pressed by hand in an aluminum crucible. A 20 mL min⁻¹ nitrogen flow was used to ensure an inert atmosphere during measurements. The samples were heated to target temperatures with a ramping rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. T_m and T_g are defined as the intersection of the starting baseline and the tangent to the DSC curve at the maximum gradient point.

C_p Scan: To obtain the C_p scan, a Netzsch STA 449 F1 instrument was used. The PZGC-05Cp sample was heated to 380 °C at a rate of 20 °C min⁻¹. A baseline and a sapphire reference scan were performed prior to the sample scan using the same temperature program. To ensure the

requested thermal conductivity, 22 mg of blended PZGC-05C_p powder was placed in an aluminum crucible and melted at 450 °C with heating and cooling rates of 10 °C min⁻¹.

Digital Optical Microscopy: A Keyence VHX-6000 digital microscope with a VH-Z100UR lens was used as a differential interference contrast lens and the images were captured by focal scanning along the z-axis and stacking. Top lights with a top-lit, side-lit, and bottom-lit lighting configuration were set to capture the images with variable magnifications.

Heating Stage + Microscope: The sample was placed inside a small heating chamber that contained an environment of inert gas (nitrogen) and sealed using a transparent cover. A microscope was used to focus on the samples through the lid. The furnace was heated to a temperature of 450 °C and then kept at that temperature for a period of 5 min before being cooled to room temperature. The images were captured in sequence during the thermal process and then used to compile a visual recording of the entire heating, holding, and cooling process. Movie S1 (Supporting Information) was recorded using a NIKON LV 100 UDM microscope equipped with a Nikon 20x TU Plan Fluor objective and assembled using NIS-Elements AR 4.3 (Nikon software). Movies S2 (Supporting Information) and S3 (Supporting Information) were captured with a Zeiss AXIO Imager Z1 m microscope, using a 5x or 10x Epiplan-Neofluar objective, and compiled with the ZEN 3.5 blue edition (Zeiss software). All thermal processes were regulated by Linkam T95-HT controller units.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX): SEM images were acquired using a Schottky Field Emission Gun HR SEM JEOL JSM 7600 F. Before conducting SEM and EDX analyzes, the samples were sputtered with a 5 nm Pt coating using a sputter coater (Quorum Technologies Ltd in Germany, Q150T). For EDX measurements, an X-Max 50 mm² EDX detector developed by Oxford Instruments was employed, applying acceleration voltages within the range of 15–20 kV. To perform elemental analysis and color mapping, the Aztec 3.1 from Oxford Instruments was paired with Channel5 software.

UV-Vis Spectroscopy: A Zeiss Axio Imager Z1 m was used in transmission illumination with an EC Epiplan-Neofluar10x/0.25 HD DIC M27 objective. One eyepiece was removed, and the light was instead coupled to an optical fiber which was connected to a solid-state spectrometer (Tristan light, UV/vis 250 nm – 850 nm + Z). The microscope lamp was set to a certain power and left for a specified period of time until its output stabilized. To avoid light passing by the sample, the field stop to the area of the sample was reduced. For the absorption measurement, the light flux Φ_s through pure a_g -ZIF-62 served as the reference sample against the doped PZGC-05 sample which the flux Φ_s through was evaluated. For the pure a_g -ZIF-62 and PZGC-1 samples, blank measurement was used as the reference light flux Φ_r . The absorption (Abs) was calculated using Equation 1.

$$A = -\log_{10} (\Phi_s / \Phi_r) \quad (1)$$

Raman spectroscopy: Raman spectra for the a_g -ZIF-62 and PZGC-30 samples were collected using the Renishaw inVia 66C507 Raman microscope with an objective x20 and excitation wavelength of 633 nm. The samples were placed on a glass slide. Spectra were collected in the wavenumber range of 500–1650 cm⁻¹. The resulting spectra were processed in the Renishaw WiRe 4.0 for easy comparison. Baseline corrections were applied to the bare measurement curves.

Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy: To collect FTIR spectra, an attenuated total reflection (ATR) module (PIKE Technologies GladiATR) was used in a PerkinElmer Spectrum 3 FT-IR Spectrometer. For the background spectra, a total of 64 scans were recorded, while 128 scans were recorded for the sample spectra, with a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹.

Impedance Spectroscopy: The surface areas of PZGC-20 and PZGC-30 were calculated with ImageJ analysis using the photographs of measured pieces (Figure S9, Supporting Information) as ≈0.572 and ≈0.209 cm². The sample thicknesses were measured by microscope for PZGC-20, PZGC-30, and PZGC-50 as ≈0.50, ≈0.54, and ≈1.49 mm respectively (Figure S4, Supporting Information). The impedance measurements were performed in a Novocontrol Alpha-A spectrometer paired with a Novotherm Temperature Control System. The frequency range was set

from 10^{-1} to 10^7 Hz and the temperature was set from 100 to 200 °C for PZGC-10, PZGC-20, and PZGC-30 with intervals of 20 °C.

The atmosphere-controlled impedance measurements of PZGC-50 were conducted using the Solartron Analytical Modulab Impedance Spectrometer inside the NorECs As ProbatTM-A chamber equipped with circular Pt electrodes (surface area ≈ 0.159 cm²), maintaining the same temperature settings and frequency range from 10^{-1} to 10^6 Hz. The chamber temperature was regulated by Lenton Thermal Designs. A constant flow of technical CO₂, Ar, and ambient air was supplied to the chamber at 200 °C for impedance measurements in the controlled atmosphere. The flow pressure of CO₂ and Ar was manually set within the range of 17–18 mbar and monitored using a Digima LP pressure meter (Special Instruments mod. 190). Ambient air was introduced into the chamber using a Maxima R pump, maintaining a pressure of 96 mbar.

Resistance under direct current (R_{DC}) was determined as the right intersection of the x-axis with the half circle of the Nyquist Plot (real and imaginary part of the impedance, Z' vs Z''), see Figure S8 (Supporting Information), Figure 3. The conductivity (σ) was calculated as given in Equation 2:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{R_{DC}} \frac{l}{A} \quad (2)$$

where l is the thickness and A is the area of the sample.

The temperature dependence of the conductivity was described by the Arrhenius relation in Equation 3:

$$\sigma T = \sigma_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{k_B T}\right) \quad (3)$$

where σ_0 is the prefactor, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and E_a is the activation energy of the conductivity.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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composite, electroactive sensor, hybrid glass, MOF glass

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